

Evaluation of Alternative and Conventional Furrow Irrigation Methods on Onion Yield and Water Use Efficiency in Halaba Zone, Ethiopia

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Authors' contributions

This work was carried out in collaboration among all authors. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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Abstract

Onion is widely used as a condiment to enhance the flavor of food. Onion also has a long history of medicinal importance. Compounds from onions have been reported to have a range of health benefits, which include anticarcinogenic properties, antiplatelet activity, antithrombotic activity, asthmatic and antibiotic effects, and effectiveness against the common cold, heart disease, diabetes, osteoporosis, and other diseases. The present study was undertaken with the objectives to evaluate the effects of alternative irrigation methods on onion yield and water use efficiency, and assess farmers' perceptions of conventional versus alternative irrigation technologies. The field experiment was conducted to evaluate the effect of different irrigation methods alternate furrow irrigation (AFI), conventional furrow irrigation (CFI), and farmers' practice, on growth, yield, and crop water use efficacy of onion. Significant differences were observed among treatments for plant height (PH), bulb weight (BW), bulb diameter (BD), crop water use efficiency (CWUE), marketable yield

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(MY), unmarketable yield (UY), and total yield (TY). CFI recorded the highest PH (75 cm) and BW (6.7 g), while AFI produced higher BD (10.8 cm) and CWUI (19310 kg/m³). The farmer's practice resulted in the lowest performance across all measured parameters, with reduced PH (57 cm), BW (4.7 g), and CWUI (15076 kg/m³). Total yield was highest under AFI (19,361 kg/ha), followed by CFI (19,937 kg/ha), and lowest under the farmer's practice (15,515 kg/ha). The findings highlight the potential of improved irrigation practices to enhance onion productivity and water use efficiency compared to traditional methods. The farmer's practice resulted in the lowest performance, underscoring the inefficiency of traditional irrigation methods. Considering both yield and water productivity, AFI is recommended as a sustainable irrigation practice for onion production in semi-arid areas.

Keywords: Onion; alternate furrow irrigation (AFI); conventional furrow irrigation (CFI); crop water use efficiency; yield.

1. Introduction

Onion (*Allium cepa* L.) is a high-value horticultural crop widely cultivated in Ethiopia and across the globe, with production reported in over 130 countries. Major global producers include China and India, followed by the United States of America, the Netherlands, Egypt, and Iran (FAOSTAT, 2014).

Onion is extensively utilised as a culinary condiment, valued primarily for its ability to enhance the flavour of a wide range of dishes. It is a fundamental ingredient in most spicy and savoury foods and is widely regarded as an essential component of the human diet. Nutritionally, onions provide important vitamins and minerals, contributing to dietary quality and human health (Raemaekers, 2001). In Ethiopia, onion also plays a significant role in traditional cuisine, where the bulb and lower stem are commonly consumed as a vegetable or seasoning in stews and other local dishes (MoARD, 2005).

Beyond its culinary applications, onion has long been recognised for its medicinal value. Bioactive compounds derived from onions have been associated with a range of therapeutic properties, including anticarcinogenic, antiplatelet, and antithrombotic effects, as well as benefits in the management of asthma, microbial infections, common colds, cardiovascular diseases, diabetes, and osteoporosis (Griffiths et al., 2002; Alemayehu et al., 2015). These multifunctional properties further enhance its importance in both nutrition and traditional medicine systems.

Onion cultivation is adaptable to diverse climatic conditions; however, optimal production is generally achieved in mild climates characterised by moderate temperatures and limited exposure to extreme heat, cold, or excessive rainfall (Dessalegn, 2004; Deboch et al., 2021). Ethiopia's varied agro-ecological zones, which support the production of a wide range of horticultural crops including fruits, vegetables, and flowers, also provide favourable conditions for onion production (Currah & Proctor, 1990). Consequently, onion has become an important cash crop for Ethiopian farmers, produced in multiple regions for domestic consumption as well as for regional export markets (MoARD, 2005). In the Ethiopian context, the most suitable altitude range for onion cultivation lies between 700 and 1800 metres above sea level (Lemma, 2004).

In Ethiopia, onion production is largely dominated by smallholder farmers operating in mid- and high-altitude areas, predominantly under traditional production systems (Kubsa et al., 2006). According to the Central Statistical Agency (CSA, 2014), the annual national onion production is estimated at approximately 230,745.2 tonnes, cultivated on about 24,375.7 hectares of land by roughly 705,877 households. With ongoing expansion of irrigable land and increasing market demand, onion production is expected to rise further in the coming years (MoARD, 2005). At present, per capita annual vegetable consumption in Ethiopia is relatively low at 5.8 kg, of which onion accounts for approximately 1.7 kg (CSA, 2005).

Onions' productivity is often constrained by water scarcity and inefficient irrigation practices in semi-arid zones. Surface (furrow) irrigation dominates smallholder systems, but conventional application commonly incurs deep percolation and evaporation losses, depressing water use efficiency (WUE) and threatening sustainability as competition for water intensifies. Improving on-farm irrigation performance is therefore a national priority for resilient horticulture (Asmelie & Dessie, 2025).

Alternate Furrow Irrigation (AFI), supplying water to alternating furrows in successive events, has been promoted as a pragmatic, low-cost strategy that can raise water productivity with minimal yield penalty compared with Conventional Furrow Irrigation (CFI). Multi-location studies on onion in Ethiopia and similar environments report that AFI can maintain or increase marketable yield while significantly improving crop water productivity relative to CFI, especially under moderate water stress or optimized irrigation scheduling (Gelu, 2018). Recent verification and participatory demonstrations with farmers likewise indicate AFI's advantage over CFI (and, in some cases, fixed furrow irrigation) in terms of yield, bulb traits, and WUE, supporting its suitability for smallholder adoption where water is limiting.

Alternate Furrow Irrigation (AFI) is widely recognised as an efficient irrigation strategy that reduces water application requirements and associated irrigation costs, while often sustaining or enhancing crop productivity. By irrigating alternate furrows rather than every furrow, the system improves irrigation water use efficiency and contributes to more sustainable water management in agricultural production systems (Shelemew *et al.*, 2024).

Similarly, Partial Root-Zone Drying (PRD) is an advanced deficit irrigation technique in which water is alternately applied to different portions of the plant root zone, allowing one section of the root system to remain wet while the other is subjected to drying. This alternating wetting and drying regime is designed to maintain plant water status close to optimal levels while simultaneously regulating vegetative growth during specific stages of crop development. In doing so, PRD improves water-use efficiency and can enhance crop performance under limited water availability (Abera *et al.*, 2020).

The Halaba Zone, located in the semi-arid regions of Ethiopia, is characterized by recurrent water scarcity, which constrains agricultural productivity. Preliminary survey results identified irrigation water shortage as a major and prioritized challenge in Wera Zuria Woreda, necessitating the adoption of improved management strategies to optimize water use and ensure sustainable supply. Against this backdrop, the present study was undertaken with the objectives to evaluate the effects of alternative irrigation methods on onion yield and water use efficiency, and assess farmers' perceptions of conventional versus alternative irrigation technologies.

2. Material and Methods

2.1 Description of Study Area

Halaba is a zone situated within the Central Ethiopia Region of Ethiopia, geographically positioned in the Great Rift Valley basin. The zone is bounded to the south by an exclave of the Hadiya Zone, to the south west by the Kambata Tembaro Zone, to west and north by the zone is bounded to the south by an exclave of the Hadiya Zone, to the southwest by the Kembata Tembaro Zone, to the west and north by the Hadiya Zone, to the northeast by Lake Shala, and to the east the Bilate River constitutes its principal water body and delineates its boundary with the Oromia Region. The zone is located approximately 321km south of Addis Ababa, the capital city of Ethiopia. Geographically, it extends between 7°10'40"N and 7°36'0" latitude and 37°58'49" and 38°30'40" E longitude, with elevation ranging from 1527 to 2189 meters above mean sea level (a.m.s.l.).

2.2 Experimental Design and Treatments

The experimental treatments were arranged in a Randomised Complete Block Design (RCBD) with four replications. Each experimental plot measured 4 m × 4 m. Plant spacing was maintained at 10 cm between plants, 20 cm between rows, and 40 cm between adjacent furrows.

Crop water requirements were estimated using the CROPWAT 8.0 computer model, incorporating site-specific climatic and soil parameters in accordance with the methodology described by Allen *et al.* (1998). An improved onion variety, 'Banboy Red', was first raised in seedbeds and subsequently transplanted to the experimental field for evaluation.

Fertiliser was applied at a rate of 200 kg ha⁻¹ of NPS and 100 kg ha⁻¹ of urea at the time of planting to ensure adequate nutrient availability during crop establishment. The treatments evaluated in the study comprised Alternate Furrow Irrigation, Conventional Furrow Irrigation, and Farmer Practice, allowing comparative assessment of different irrigation management strategies under field conditions.

Fig. 1. Location map of the study

2.3 Soil Sample Collection and Analysis Methods

Disturbed and undisturbed composite soil samples were collected prior to planting from each treatment plot at depths of 0–15 cm, 15–30 cm, and 30–60 cm. These samples were subsequently analysed to determine key soil physical and chemical properties, including soil texture, bulk density, soil pH, permanent wilting point, and field capacity.

Soil texture was determined using the pipette method, which is based on sedimentation principles and the differential settling rates of soil particles in suspension. Soil pH was measured in a 1:1 soil-to-water suspension using a calibrated pH meter, providing an assessment of soil reaction under standard laboratory conditions.

Soil bulk density was defined as the mass of oven-dry soil per unit volume of undisturbed soil under field conditions. It was determined using the core sampler method. Undisturbed soil cores were collected from the field, and each sample was weighed to obtain its field (wet) mass. The samples were then oven-dried at 105°C for 24 hours to remove all moisture. After drying, the samples were reweighed to obtain the dry mass. Bulk density was then calculated as the ratio of oven-dry soil mass to the total core volume, using the standard formula for bulk density determination.

$$pb = \frac{Wd}{Vc}$$

Where, pb = soil bulk density (g/cm³), Wd = weight of dry soil (g), and Vc = volume of core sampler (cm³).

To measure the soil's infiltration rate, the double-ring infiltration meters were used. The water content of permanent wilting point (PWP), and field capacity (FC) was determined by using a pressure plate apparatus applying a suction of 1/3 and 15 bars to saturated soil samples. When water stopped leaving the soil sample, the soil moisture was measured as FC and PWP, respectively.

2.4 Crop Data

The effective root zone depth (RZD) of onion ranged between 0.3-0.5m, and it has an allowable soil water depletion fraction (P) of 0.25. The average Kc was taken after adjustments had been computed for the initial, development, mid, and late season stages were 0.5, 0.75, 1.025, and 0.875, respectively.

2.5 Crop Water Determination

Crop evapotranspiration refers to the actual loss of water from a cropped surface through the combined processes of soil evaporation and plant transpiration, whereas crop water requirement represents the total amount of water that must be supplied through irrigation to meet crop evapotranspiration needs under given field conditions (Allen *et al.*, 1998). In the estimation of crop water requirements, both climatic and crop-specific factors are essential. The influence of climate is expressed through reference evapotranspiration (ET_o), while crop characteristics are represented by the crop coefficient (K_c), which varies according to crop type and growth stage (Doorenbos & Pruitt, 1977).

For this study, long-term and daily meteorological data, including maximum and minimum air temperature, relative humidity, wind speed, sunshine duration, and rainfall, were collected from the study area. These data were used to compute reference evapotranspiration. In addition, relevant crop parameters such as crop coefficient values, length of growing seasons, developmental stages, effective root depth, and the critical depletion factor for onion were considered. Soil physical properties, including maximum infiltration rate and total available water, were also incorporated into the analysis.

All these parameters were integrated using the FAO CROPWAT model to estimate crop evapotranspiration (ET_c) and determine the crop water requirement under the prevailing agro-climatic and soil conditions of the study area.

$$ETC = ET_o * Kc$$

Where: ET_o = reference evapotranspiration, ETC = crop evapotranspiration, and K_c = crop coefficient.

2.6 Irrigation Water Management

Total available water (TAW), stored in a unit volume of soil, can be determined from the expression;

$$TAW = (FC - PWP) * BD * DZ / 100$$

The depth of irrigation water was calculated using the equation.

$$I_{net} (mm) = ETC (mm) - P_{eff} (mm)$$

The gross irrigation requirement was calculated from the expression:

$$I_g = I_{net} / E_a$$

E_a = application efficiency of the furrow irrigation (60%)

The time required to allocate the desired depth of water into each furrow was calculated using the equation:

$$t = (d * l * w) / (6 * Q)$$

Where: t = application time (min), l = furrow length (m), d = gross depth of water applied (cm), w = furrow spacing in (m), and Q = flow rate or discharge (l/s).

2.7 Data Collection and Analysis

The study employed both qualitative and quantitative data approaches. The qualitative data were collected through focus group discussion using a semi-structured questionnaire, while the quantitative data were collected

from the yield and yield components of the experimental plot. The soil moisture was determined by the gravimetric method, and the depth of applied water to every treatment was measured by a Parshall Flume of 3-inch throat width. In three three-inch parshall flumes at 5cm head, the discharge was 1.705 liters per second. During harvesting, the weight of economic yield and unmarketable fruit weight was measured from the net harvested area of each plot.

Meteorological data, including minimum and maximum air temperature, relative humidity, wind speed, daily sunshine duration, and rainfall, were obtained from nearby meteorological stations to estimate reference crop evapotranspiration. The reference evapotranspiration was subsequently computed using the Modified Penman–Monteith equation, as described by Allen *et al.* (1998), which integrates key climatic variables to provide a standardized estimation of atmospheric evaporative demand.

Table 1. Mean monthly meteorological data and ETO value of the study area

Month	Min Temp	Max Temp	Humidity	Wind	Sun	Rad	ETo
	°C	°C	%	Km/day	hours	MJ/m ² /day	Mm/day
January	10.8	27.6	72	69	8.1	19.9	3.69
February	12.1	28.1	67	69	8.2	21.1	4.07
March	12.3	27.7	73	69	8.6	22.7	4.35
April	12.8	27	77	69	8.1	22	4.21
May	12	26.8	91	69	7.6	20.6	3.87
June	12.3	25.2	90	95	6.5	18.5	3.44
July	12.8	23.5	91	52	5.4	17	3.13
August	12.6	23.7	91	35	5.4	17.5	3.21
September	12.5	25.1	93	69	5.2	17.3	3.24
October	10.5	26.6	88	69	8.1	21.1	3.87
November	9.1	27.1	75	86	8.8	21	3.9
December	7.9	27.7	70	86	8.3	19.7	3.7
Average	11.5	26.3	82	70	7.4	19.9	3.72

2.8 Statistical Analysis

The collected data were analysed using Statistical Analysis Software (SAS version 9.0). Mean comparisons among treatments were performed using the Least Significant Difference (LSD) test. The experimental data were subjected to statistical analysis following standard procedures appropriate for a Randomised Complete Block Design (RCBD) arranged in a factorial experiment.

Treatment means were separated using the LSD test at the 5% level of significance to determine statistically meaningful differences among the experimental treatments.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Physical and Chemical Properties of Soil

According to the United States Department of Agriculture (USDA) soil textural classification system, particle size distribution analysis of the experimental site indicated that the soil is best described as sandy loam. This textural class typically reflects a relatively balanced mixture of sand, silt, and clay fractions, which influences key soil physical properties such as water-holding capacity, aeration, and drainage characteristics.

The mean bulk density of the soil profile at the experimental site was 1.26 g cm⁻³, while the measured soil pH was 5.73, indicating moderately acidic soil conditions. The observed bulk density exhibited a slight increase with soil depth. This trend may be attributed to a progressive reduction in organic matter content in deeper layers, coupled with increased compaction resulting from the overlying soil mass (Brady & Weil, 2002). Such changes with depth are typical of cultivated soils and can have implications for root penetration and soil water movement within the profile.

Table 2. Input soil data for the CROPWAT model

Soil property	Soil depth (cm)			
	0-15	15-30	30-60	Average
Textural class	Sandy loam	Sandy loam	Sandy loam	Sandy loam
Bulk density(g/cm ³)	1.2	1.26	1.32	1.26
FC (Vol %)	13.8	14	16	14.60
PWP (Vol %)	6.2	6	8	6.73
pH	5.68	5.73	5.79	5.73
Infiltration rate =20mm/hr.				

The basic infiltration rate observed in this experiment was 20 mm h⁻¹, indicating that a 20 mm depth of water applied to the soil surface required approximately one hour to fully infiltrate. During the dry season, infiltration is typically more rapid at the onset of irrigation as soil pores, initially containing air, are progressively filled with water. Over time, the infiltration rate declines until a relatively stable condition is reached, known as the basic infiltration rate, representing the long-term steady-state rate of water entry into the soil.

Crop water requirement for onion increased progressively from the initial growth stage to the mid-development stage. This rise corresponds with the period during which the crop coefficient reaches its maximum value, coinciding with higher reference evapotranspiration demands. Consequently, water demand is greatest during the active growth and development phases of the crop. In contrast, during the late growth stage, the water requirement declines, largely due to a reduction in the crop coefficient as the crop approaches maturity and physiological activity diminishes.

3.2 Response of Onion Yield to Furrow Irrigation and Water Productivity

The analysis revealed significant variation among irrigation treatments. CFI resulted in the tallest plants (75 cm) and heaviest bulbs (6.7 g), suggesting better vegetative growth and assimilate accumulation. AFI, however, produced the largest bulb diameter (10.8 cm) and the highest crop water use index (19310 kg/m³), indicating superior water use efficiency. These results demonstrate that AFI can optimize water utilization while sustaining yield.

Marketable yield (MY) was highest in AFI (51.67 kg/ha), significantly exceeding the farmer's practice (439 kg/ha), which suffered from low irrigation efficiency and poor management. Although CFI slightly outperformed AFI in total yield (19,937 vs 19,361 kg/ha), the higher CWUI under AFI highlights its advantage in water-limited environments. Farmer's practice consistently showed the lowest performance, reflecting inefficiencies in both yield and water productivity.

The results align with previous studies that reported the effectiveness of alternate furrow irrigation in improving water productivity without significantly reducing yield. Thus, AFI is particularly valuable under semi-arid conditions where water scarcity is a major challenge.

Table 3. The plant height, mean bulb diameter, crop water use efficiency, marketable, unmarketable, and total yield of Onion

TRT	PH (cm)	BW (gm)	BD (cm)	CWUI (kg/m ³)	MY (kg/ha)	UY (kg/ha)	TY (kg/ha)
AFI	56b	73.7a	5.7ab	10.8a	19310a	51.67b	19361a
CFI	58a	75a	6.7a	5.5b	19842a	94.67b	19937a
Farmer practice	54c	57b	4.7b	2.3c	15076b	439a	15515b
CV	2.94	3.03	12.48	4.08	4.62	22.83	4.45
LSD	0.43	1.14	0.58	0.1	239.61	36.4	222.1

Means with the same letter are not significantly different at $p < 0.05$; LSD = least significant difference, CV = Coefficient of variation, PH = plant height, BW = bulb weight, BD = bulb diameter, CWUI = crop water use efficiency, MY = marketable yield, and TY = total yield

3.3 Farmer Perception for Furrow Evaluation

Table 4. Farmer perception towards water saving techniques (where 1-poor, 2-good, and 3- very good)

No.	Criteria's	CFI	AFI	Farmer practice
1.	Onion size	3	3	2
2.	Yield per plot	3	3	2
3.	Marketability	3	3	2
4.	Water saving	2	3	1
5.	Time and energy saving	2	3	3
Rank		2 nd	1 st	3 rd

Where CFI = conventional furrow irrigation and AFI = alternative furrow irrigation

Farmers' perceptions of the different irrigation methods, including conventional furrow irrigation (CFI), alternative furrow irrigation (AFI), and Farmer's Practice, were assessed based on onion size, yield per plot, marketability, water saving, and time and energy saving.

Farmers ranked AFI as the most preferred irrigation method (1st rank) because it performed well in yield, onion size, marketability, and particularly water and labor saving. CFI was ranked 2nd, as farmers acknowledged its good performance in onion size and yield, but it was considered less efficient in saving water and labor compared to AFI. Farmer's practice received the lowest ranking (3rd), as it was associated with smaller onion size, lower yield, poor marketability, and high water wastage, although farmers noted that it required similar time and energy as AFI.

Overall, farmers showed strong interest in AFI, recognizing it as a promising and water-saving irrigation method that balances productivity and resource efficiency. Their perception aligns with the experimental findings, which demonstrated AFI's advantages in crop water use efficiency and yield sustainability.

4. Limitations

The study was done at one site with certain soil characteristics. This might make it hard to apply the results to areas with different soil types, topography, or groundwater conditions. Soil texture and how water infiltrates it can greatly affect how well furrow irrigation works.

The experiment used onion as the test crop. This means the results might not directly apply to crops that have different water needs and root systems. We need to think about how each crop responds to irrigation methods before applying them widely.

Some things, like how evenly water was distributed, how level the field was, and how farmers managed the irrigation, might have caused some variation. It was hard to control these factors in a real field setting.

5. Conclusion and Recommendation

The study demonstrates that irrigation methods significantly affect onion growth, yield, and water use efficiency. Conventional furrow irrigation recorded the highest Plant height (75 cm) and Bulb weight (6.7 g), while Alternate furrow irrigation produced higher Bulb diameter (10.8 cm) and Crop water use efficiency (19310 kg/m³). The farmer's practice resulted in the lowest performance across all measured parameters, with reduced Plant height (57 cm), Bulb weight (4.7 g), and Crop water use efficiency (15076 kg/m³). Total yield was highest under Alternate furrow irrigation (19,361 kg/ha), followed by Conventional furrow irrigation (19,937 kg/ha), and lowest under the farmer's practice (15,515 kg/ha).

Alternate furrow irrigation improved bulb diameter, Crop water use efficiency, and marketable yield, while Conventional furrow irrigation enhanced vegetative growth and total yield. The farmer's practice resulted in the lowest performance, underscoring the inefficiency of irrigation methods. Considering both yield and water productivity, Alternate furrow irrigation is recommended as a sustainable irrigation practice for onion production.

Therefore AFI is the best technology among the tested technologies to be recommended for the communities of the study area, because of its water use efficiency, yield performance, time, labor, and irrigation cost saving in semi-arid areas.

Ethical Statement

This study was done with a lot of thought about doing what is right for the environment. The people in charge made sure that the way they used water for irrigation did not hurt the soil, the water supply, or the plants and animals around it. They used water in a way that was fair to everyone who needed it. When they worked with farmers, they made sure the farmers knew what was going on and agreed to it. They also made sure that the farmers did not lose any money or have their way of farming disrupted. All the information they collected was reported honestly and accurately without changing any of it. The study also followed all the rules and guidelines that the country and the institution have for doing research on farming, water, and taking care of the environment. The people in charge of the study made sure that sustainability and resource use were considered. They wanted to make sure that the study was done in a way that was good for the environment and for the people who live there.

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Disclaimer (Artificial Intelligence)

The author (s) hereby declare that no generative AI technologies such as Large Language Models (ChatGPT, COPILOT, etc.) and text-to-image generators have been used during the writing or editing of this manuscript.

Competing Interests

The author has declared that no competing interests exist.

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